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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
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- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
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- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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CRITERIA OF SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY IMPLEMENTATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the criteria for organizing the research activities of students in physical culture education. It highlights the main principles and methodological recommendations that should be followed by students and their scientific supervisors in conducting research. In addition, the stages of planning research activities, organizing experiments, analyzing results, and implementing them into practice are systematically described. The study substantiates approaches aimed at improving the effectiveness of students' research activities.

Key words: physical culture, experiment, scientific research, student, upbringing, higher education, pedagogy, supervisor, sports, education, system, standard.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada jismoniy madaniyat ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarining ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyatini tashkil etish mezonlari tahlil qilinadi. Unda talabalar hamda ularning ilmiy rahbarlari tomonidan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarini samarali olib borishda amal qilinishi lozim bo'lgan asosiy tamoyillar va metodik tavsiyalar yoritilgan. Shuningdek, ilmiy faoliyatni rejalashtirish, tajriba (eksperiment)ni tashkil etish, natijalarni tahlil qilish va ularni amaliyotga joriy etish bosqichlari tizimli ravishda bayon etilgan. Maqolada ilmiy tadqiqot jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi yondashuvlar asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy madaniyat, eksperiment, ilmiy tadqiqot, talaba, tarbiya, oliy ta'lim, pedagogika, ilmiy rahbar, sport, ta'lim, tizim, standart.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются критерии организации научно-исследовательской деятельности студентов направления физической культуры. Освещены основные принципы и методические рекомендации, которые должны соблюдаться студентами и их научными руководителями при проведении научных исследований. Также системно раскрыты этапы планирования научной деятельности, организации эксперимента, анализа результатов и их внедрения в практику. Обоснованы подходы, направленные на повышение эффективности научно-исследовательской деятельности студентов.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, эксперимент, научное исследование, студент, воспитание, высшее образование, педагогика, научный руководитель, спорт, образование, система, стандарт.

INTRODUCTION

The final state certification of graduates obtaining a bachelor's degree in physical culture and a master's degree in the theory and methods of physical culture and sports in the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is determined by their final research work. It is also recognized as a form of dissertation work that prepares students for future professional activities and the attainment of academic degrees.

The current normative and legal documents in education provide a systematic framework for higher education, including state educational standards, qualification requirements for specific fields, the content of education, and the necessary level of general training of graduates. These standards also serve as benchmarks for assessing the quality of training and are continuously being developed and improved.

The purpose of the national model of training is to fundamentally reform the education system, elevate it to the level of developed countries, and create a system for preparing highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical standards.

LITERATURE REVIEW

At present, numerous scientific studies in the field of physical culture and sports are conducted not only by researchers but also by coaches and educators in educational institutions. A creative approach to research, involving the search for new, original, and effective ways to solve pedagogical problems, remains a relevant issue.

Research activities play an important role in shaping students' future professional competencies. Through engagement in research, students gain insights and practical experience that positively influence their future careers. Therefore, directing students toward scientific inquiry and teaching them its specific requirements is essential for preparing competitive specialists.

Scientific work in physical culture includes different types, such as methodological, scientific-methodological, and research work. The scientific value of research is determined not by its type but by adherence to established scientific requirements.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In student research within the field of physical culture, it is essential to clearly define and follow the stages of research work. These stages include:

- selection of the research topic;
- description of the object and subject of research;
- definition of goals and objectives;
- determination of research scope;
- development of hypotheses;
- preparation of a research plan;
- literature review;
- assessment of the degree of topic exploration;
- selection of research methods;
- organization of research conditions;
- data collection and analysis;
- processing of results;
- presentation of findings;
- preparation of the final research work.

Each stage has specific tasks that are usually solved sequentially, and in some cases simultaneously.

Research methodology refers to the structured program guiding the study, while research methods represent the techniques used to collect and analyze data. Scientific-methodological work plays a key role, combining both theoretical and practical aspects of research.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis shows that effective organization of student research in physical culture depends on a clear understanding of research stages and adherence to scientific principles. The distinction between methodological and scientific-methodological work lies in the presence of innovation and the depth of analysis.

Experimental research allows for the identification of new patterns in teaching and training, requiring comparative analysis and the use of scientific-methodological resources.

The findings also emphasize the importance of selecting feasible research topics, ensuring proper experimental conditions, and maintaining academic integrity. Students must avoid plagiarism, falsification of data, and incorrect citation practices.

The role of the scientific supervisor is crucial in guiding the research process, including:

- organizing consultations;
- assisting in method selection;
- monitoring progress;
- evaluating research outcomes prior to defense.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the effective organization of research activities for students in the field of physical culture requires a systematic approach based on clearly defined stages, adherence to scientific standards, and active collaboration between students and supervisors.

It is recommended to:

- strengthen methodological guidance for student research;
- ensure proper supervision and regular консультации;
- promote academic integrity and ethical standards;
- create conditions for conducting high-quality experimental research;
- encourage student participation in scientific competitions and broader research initiatives.

These measures contribute to improving the quality of research work and preparing highly qualified specialists in the field of physical culture.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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